

FDM 3D-Printing in High-Pressure Oxygen and Pure Nitrogen Atmospheres & Evaluation of Mechanical Properties

by

Yousuf Pasha Shaik

University of Applied Sciences Kaiserslautern, Germany

Institute for Polymer Technology Westpalatinate

Objective

Problems - FDM

- 1) Voids
- 2) Oxidation of layers
- 3) Weak bonding
- 4) Warping

Fig. 1 SEM image of the 3D Printed sample

Approach - 3D Printer situated in the Autoclave

Autoclave ; 135 bar &
180 °C temperature
can be maintained

Cooling coils

FDM-printer
[Ender 3 V2]
with PLA - spool

635 mm

All cables (app. 60) are
guided outside of the
autoclave through special
connectors.

Fig. 2 3D Printer in the autoclave

Experimental plan - 3D Printing in the Autoclave

- 3D printing in an autoclave at 0 bar, 5 bar, 10 bar, 15 bar, 20 bar in compressed air, and 5 bar in a Nitrogen atmosphere
- Material: PLA [Herz GmbH] – Granules & Filament
- Autoclave temperature = 50°C
- Nozzle diameter = 0.5 mm
- Printing speed = 100%
- Layer thickness = 0.15 mm
- Hot end temperature = 200°C
- Bed temperature = 60°C

Modulus - longitudinal pattern

- ❖ Young's modulus comparison of samples printed in the longitudinal direction in different pressure conditions with injection molded samples

Test standard: DIN EN ISO 527-1

Modulus - transverse pattern

- ❖ Young's modulus comparison of samples printed in the transverse direction in different pressure conditions with injection molded samples

Test standard: DIN EN ISO 527-1

Yield strength - longitudinal pattern

- ❖ Yield strength comparison of samples printed in the longitudinal direction in different pressure conditions with injection molded samples

Test standard: DIN EN ISO 527-1

Yield strength - transverse pattern

- ❖ Yield strength comparison of samples printed in the transverse direction in different pressure conditions with injection molded samples

Test standard: DIN EN ISO 527-1

Microscopy test results

At 0 bar

At 5 bar

At 10 bar

At 15 bar

At 20 bar

Injection molded

Conclusion

- ❖ Mechanical strength increased
- ❖ Reduce voids
- ❖ Better layer adhesion
- ❖ Material density increment
- ❖ Surface finish

Thank You for Listening

Any Questions?

